

Contextual Spacetime and the Making of Classical Reality - Part 3: How Measurements Cause Time

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The Infinite Whole

Objectively, there is only an infinite whole. The infinite whole by itself cannot contain any objective entities within it as any separations of the infinite whole would need to be subjectively based. After all, in order for there to be a separation of entities within the infinite whole, there needs to be a “starting point” of such a separation. For example, if one were to cut a paper into different sized “sub-papers” they would need to choose a spot on the paper to make a first cut.

The issue with the infinite whole is that it cannot be compared to a paper because it is not still and contained like a paper is. A paper for example can be objectively separated at its midpoint and cut in such a way where there will be 2 resulting sub-papers of the same size. The infinite whole however expands infinitely in every possible direction so cannot be given a midpoint. Instead any cut to the infinite whole must be done so based purely subjectively without knowledge of “where” in the topology of the infinite whole the cut is done. This is because, if the infinite whole expands infinitely in every direction, there can be no knowledge of where its midpoint is or any other corresponding location. Unlike the paper, its topology is “inconceivable”. Therefore there is no way to “objectively” cut or identify entities within the context of the infinite whole. Instead any cut to the infinite whole must be subjective based on the subjective “starting point of the cut”. Therefore any “entity” that is ever defined as existing must exist only “subjectively” and not “objectively”.

Informational Entities

Objectively, the infinite whole can consist of any “information” possible. For example, there are an “infinite” amount of numbers that can be conceived of objectively. This “infinite” amount of numbers could not even be “divided” or “split” because it grows infinitely fast. For if one wanted to divide these numbers into 3 sets for example, there would be no way to do so since the set of numbers between 0 and infinity could not have a contained magnitude that could ever be divided (since it expands infinitely fast in 0 time).

The infinite whole would also need to include every single possible conceivable piece of information. This means that not only must everything physical be contained within the infinite whole but also anything imaginable and conceivable.

Generating a Random Number From an Infinite Set

Now say that one wanted to “choose” a number between 0 and infinity. Ordinarily, this “number selection” would be biased as a person would be more likely to choose a lower number than a higher number as they are unable to count to or conceive of. However, say that such a number was truly objectively chosen and had the same probability of being any number from 0 to infinity.

This would mean that there would be an infinite amount of potential eigenstates for such a number before it was chosen. For before the number was chosen, the number could be “fundamentally any number from 0 to infinity”. The probability of any number X being the correct number would therefore be $1/\text{infinity}$. Now say that one wanted to add every possible number to a list that they can iterate over until reaching the correct number. Obviously this would be impossible, as an infinite amount of numbers could not be contained in a list (since there would always need to be more numbers higher than the highest number in the list).

Generating a Random Number From a Finite Set

Now say that one was selecting a number from 1-10. One could simply create a list with the numbers 0-10 and then iterate over each of the 10 numbers until finding the correct number. If one iterates over say 7 numbers before reaching the correct number (7), this would mean that there were essentially 7 separate instances of “comparing” the proposed number to the correct number. IE - on the first iteration, one could ask the program - “is 1 the correct number?” When the response is no (because 1 isn't 7) they can go on to the next number and so on.

Each iteration of counting in this case is essentially a “division of time”. In the case of 10 numbers, it can be said that “10 instances of time” would need to exist in order to iterate over the 10 numbers. This is because 10 “measurements” must be made and they cannot all be made at the same one instance of time. This means that there can be a maximum of 10 instances of time that exist when there are 10 numbers to iterate over.

This would also mean that at any instance of time, there is a $1/10$ chance of selecting the correct number. Therefore, prior to being measured, the “correct number” can exist in only 10 possible states. However, if for example the first number is incorrect that would mean that now the correct number can only exist in 9 potential states.

It can be seen from here that time is simply a measure of measurements made. Just as there needs to be 10 instances of time when 10 comparisons need to be made to find a random number, the brain also makes trillions of measurements in order to make sense of the external world. The way time is therefore experienced by humans is by them categorizing each of those measurements into memories and then subjectively dividing them into different “units of time”. It can be seen here that the “experience of time” is always proportional to the number of measurements made by a system whether that system be a human brain or a random number program.

Shuffling of Numbers

Now say that this “correct number” was constantly changing at every moment of time due to a shuffling algorithm. For example, if there are 10 moments in time that could exist when iterating over 10 numbers, at every moment the correct number changes depending on which numbers remaining are possible. So for example at the first moment in time, the correct number could be any of the 10 numbers but when the second moment of time comes the correct number could be one of 9 numbers.

When a measurement is made, the measured number is compared to the correct number. If the number is correct, then the shuffling stops completely because the correct number could now only be one single number (the number that was chosen). If however the number was incorrect, the correct number continues shuffling between the remaining possible numbers that were not yet tried. When the correct number is chosen, one would not know if that number was the “correct number the entire time” or merely happened to become the correct number only at that moment. This is because if it always shuffled in accordance with which numbers were possible at that moment, it would not actually change anything.

(Note that the shuffling here is only meant to demonstrate an intuitive way to understand how variables can have multiple potential values at once. If a variables state is constantly “shuffling” then it essentially can have any range of values at the same instance. Only when it is actually measured does the shuffling stop causing it to collapse into one state.)

A similar idea is present in the phenomenon of quantum entanglement. If a composite particle with 0 spin breaks down into a spin up and spin down particle, when the spin up particle is measured, the other particle then “becomes” spin down (since both their spins must even out and add up to 0). Now does this mean that the particle being measured was always spin down but only was realized to be spin down when the other particle was measured as spin up? Or were both particles actually in “superpositions of both spin up and spin down states” until one particle was measured which then forced the other particle to instantaneously take on its position? John Stewart Bell conducted a series of experiments which resulted in a proof (entitled Bell’s inequality) that showed that the correlation between entangled particles is not due to hidden variables (assuming the presence of statistical independence). It can be seen from here, that the information having to do with properties of particles essentially can be thought to “shuffle” prior to being measured. This does not mean that it shuffles physically like cards do, but rather that it only exists as having potential probable properties before being conclusively measured. This ultimately shows that any information prior to being measured can be said to only “potentially exist as having certain states”. Therefore, in the case of a theoretical quantum random number generator, if the correct number being chosen is unknowable prior to measurement, it can be said to be “shuffling” potential states until it is “checked” to determine if it is correct. Every “check” in this case is a measurement which essentially constitutes a single “notice” of time.

Back to Infinite Numbers

Now apply this to the case of choosing one out of an infinite amount of numbers. When there are an infinite amount of numbers to iterate over, there are always an infinite amount of potential states for a number. For example, even after iterating over 10 numbers, there would still be an infinite amount of numbers left to count. This would mean that if the ‘correct number’ was being shuffled it would never be shuffling slower than it originally was being shuffled since there would always be an infinite amount of numbers to be shuffled over.

In my opinion, this is how the objective nature of the universe can be understood. Any possible “entity” that exists has an infinite amount of possible properties that it could eventually take on when measured just as there an infinite amount of possible numbers. However, these infinite

amount of states are always being shuffled infinitely fast since there are never “states” that can be counted out, since the potential amount of states for the property are always expanding.

This can be understood as all objective entities changing states infinitely fast (just as how the numbers in the previous case are being shuffled). However, when these objective entities states become contained, they become limited and suddenly they change states in finite time. For example, if there were only 10 possible correct numbers, now the “possibilities” for the correct numbers are “contained” and the choices are limited. This would mean it would then become “possible” to iterate over all 10 choices at 10 separate instances of time.

The Nature of Time

This is how I understand the nature of time. Time only exists as a consequence of making sense of information. For example, the only reason humans experience time is because their brains cannot make sense of information with “continuously changing potential states” so they must “divide” and iterate over the possible states of the continuously changing information in order to make sense of it. This division of the information results in a sequential step by step experiencing of information that is called “the passage of time”. Just as how when there were 10 possible states of a number, there were 10 possible instances of time, so too when there are X number of states of an entity, there are X possible instances of time that it takes to determine what that entity is. However, instead of numbers, the objective universes informational entities can be understood as “fundamental bit like particles”. Information processing systems such as the brain measure these fundamental particles states and ultimately assign them with the states that make the most sense in terms of the information that it has already recorded.

Now objectively, all entities change states infinitely fast so there can be no “sequential understanding” of their information (since they are being shuffled infinitely fast). However when there are a limited amount of states of an entity, there CAN be iteration done to slow down their shuffling and changing of states. Eventually, any entity’s changing of states can be narrowed down to only 1 state, which results in the human brain being able to measure it in a definitive state. For example, when there are 10 possible states of a number, the correct number can be surmised based off of certain factors (IE - if the numbers 1-3 were already iterated over, then it can be said that every number between 4 and 10 has a 1/7 chance of being the correct number). My claim is that any “informational particle” has its states measured by a human brain based off of information that is already known at the time of measurement that would exclude some possibilities for the unknown particles state. For example, if one part of a composite particle is measured as having an angular momentum of spin up, the other must be measured as spin down. This is because the possible informational states of angular momentum for the second particle go from two to one after the first particle is measured. This is the type of “iteration” that leads to the measurement of particles which ultimately lead to the measurement of anything in the universe made of those particles. The reason that humans experience time is because different particles states require knowledge of other particles states in order to surmise them. Therefore, the brain having to measure different particles sequentially in order to learn more about the states of different other particles results in the “experience” of a delta between the “encoded informational schemas” the brain translates the particles as.

So for example, when the brain constructs a moment of experience it does so by making measurements of a certain amount of particles and then topologically translating information about those particles into a cohesive single “experience of the world”. Therefore in order for any “moment” to happen, the brain must measure each individual particle based off of its potential states decided by the iterative measurement of the particles that its measured state is “dependent on” or “entangled” with. Because these particles each have a finite amount of potential states the brain must figure each of them out based on the measurements of other particles. This “iteration” results in different “comparison frames” which ultimately result in a delta between the experience of different particles which is what we ultimately refer to as “the passage of time”.

Why do particles in our universe have a limited amount of informational states? Why aren't they considered part of infinity?

Since any possible “counting” of a subset of infinite numbers cannot change the infinite amount of potential correct numbers, this would mean that the possible states for the number would always be infinite meaning that “counting” would not actually result in there being less potential states of the proposed number. If an infinite set of numbers are being shuffled with no progress being made, it can be said that the “correct” number is changing states infinitely fast. This is how I understand objective entities - they can be in an infinite amount of eigenstates prior to being measured, so can be considered to be “changing” infinitely fast. I consider this to happen outside of time, since time is associated with “progressively” iterating over possible informational states of a system.

Subjectively, however if one built a machine devoted solely to counting to a highest possible integer, there will be a limit as to how high a number that machine can count to. There would need to be a highest possible number the machine can count to based on 2 factors - how fast it could count and how long it could last. How fast the machine could count is bound by the speed of light as nothing in the universe can transfer information faster than the speed of light. Furthermore, while it is unknown how long the machine could last, it is assumed that there is an inherent limit to how long the universe could exist without infinitely contracting upon itself eventually. Because of these 2 factors, the machine is “limited” in terms of the highest number it could count to. Sure that number could seem to be “extremely high”, but such a “extremely high” number would still itself be finite.

This shows how our universe is essentially “limited” and cannot be infinite. If information could travel infinitely fast within our universe then the machine would reach the highest possible number in existence instantly in the absence of time. However, because the universe has a maximum speed of informational transmission that is the speed of light, the machine is inherently limited in how high a number it could count to.

I propose that this universe is therefore a “subjective subset” of the infinite whole that is finite and itself essentially “limited”. This finite-ness is what causes time itself and the finite changing states of informational entities or particles. The “speed of light” therefore defines how quickly information can change within the informational world that is this universe which is based on the universes total “potential informational states”.

For example, imagine a cursor that rests on a single coordinate of a line. In a line of size infinity the cursor can be in any possible position on the line and there would never be a way to iterate over coordinates of the line in order to find the cursor. However, if the line was QUANTIZED and finitely sized then one can finitely iterate over the line until finding the cursor. This is how I imagine the difference between the infinite whole and our universe. The infinite whole is non quantized and infinite so any “cursor” can never be found on its line. The universe is quantized and finite so with enough iteration, a “cursor” can be found.

Contextualization of the Infinite Whole

When the infinite whole is “contextualized”, a portion of the infinite whole becomes contained inside an informational world. This informational world can be likened to a finite sized box. While everything within the infinite whole is objectively “ever-changing states” infinitely fast, within the a finite sized informational world, entities could no longer change infinitely fast. Instead they are “contained” and therefore can only consist of a finite amount of properties and not an infinite amount of properties. This “finite” amount of properties that can be taken on within the limits of the informational world account for the maximum speed in which things can change within that informational world.

Informational Worlds

The universe that we are residing in is itself an “informational world” where entities cannot “change states” infinitely fast. Instead they can only change states in accordance with the total size of the informational world. This finite size of our informational world called the “universe” is sized in a way where the maximum rate of change of information needs to be confined to what is known as “the speed of light”. This speed of light not being infinite is what causes the experience of “time”. While objectively in 0 time, things can be in an infinite amount of states and therefore change infinitely fast, within the informational world of our universe there are limits to this rate of change.

Because this rate of change is not infinite, there can be a progressive iteration over the potential states of particles. This “iteration” is based off of the information known about the states of other particles they are dependent on. Particles that have definitive states cause other particles they are entangled with to only have a limited array of possible states. This “narrowing” of particles states is progressive in that different particles “number of states” changes other particles “number of states”. This shows that entanglement is present in our universe only because particles have a limited number of potential states. If they had an infinite number of potential states entanglement could never be possible because there could never be a narrowing of a particles states.

The Brain and Time

Eventually the brain can “measure” certain particles states based off of other particles states and narrow each of the particles states in a process entitled “measurement”. Measurement allows the brain to create a “box” with particles of definitive states it translates as a “moment of experience”. However, because the states of all of the particles that the brain intakes is

dependent on other particles states, the brain must create a delta in order to determine the states of different particles based on what the states of its dependent particles are. It is in my view that the brain “tying” the states of particles it observes to the states of “other particles” it observes results in the continuous nature of time that is experienced by the brains observer and also the sense of “causality”.

This “tying” of the measured states of particles cannot happen faster than the speed of light simply because the particles each have only a finite amount of states in accordance with the size of all of the particles that exist in the subjective instance of the universe.

The Universe

The universe can be thought of as an “informational world” that exists as a subjective subset of infinity. The speed of light is simply the proportional rate of change for entities that are inside of the “limited” space of the universe that itself has finite properties. The universe can therefore be thought of a “box” within infinity that essentially allows for entities inside it to take on finite properties and become real in accordance with the speed of light. Time is a result of this finite rate of change of informational entities that essentially cause them to narrow into probabilistic and definitive states under the constraints of the properties of the subjective informational world. Therefore, entities in the infinite whole can be said to be essentially “anything at once” and changing infinitely fast because they are essentially unlimited since anything within infinity never has a contained amount of potential eigenstates and therefore can never be objectively measured. However, within a “universe” there is a “limit” as to the eigenstates particles within it could take on which results in the potential “narrowing” of states of a particle into it having a finite set of properties and being measured.

When these informational entities gain definitive states they can be said to be “measured”. Measurement is essentially what causes instances of time, as the brain uses every measurement of every particle around it to construct and present an “external world” to the observer which changes at a rate proportional to the amount of measurements the brain makes. This accounts for the observation of time from the perspective of an individual. Just like for a program that iterates over numbers of a certain range in order to find the one that is arbitrarily correct, the brain also “iterates” over external information in this way in order to interpret it as having “finite states”. However, these “iterations” are realized to the observer as individual instances of time. Out of these measurements the flow of time is manufactured. The reason that information seems to be causal is because the “information” within the subjective informational world that is the universe is always itself “finite” which means any subset of it must be geometrically dependent on other subsets it relates to topologically or in “space”. Any “information processing system” such as a brain therefore needs to measure this information in a manner that assigns it as having the correct properties in relation to other properties it is dependent on. Just as puzzle pieces within a contained puzzle need to fit together based on each others pieces, information in the universe is no different. The universe itself is a puzzle within infinity and particles are its “changing pieces”. Information processing systems within the universe seek to topologically map subsets of the informational puzzle they can relate to through series of measurements.

